

EDUCATION ZONING: A MULTI-PERSPECTIVE POLICY ANALYSIS (GOVERNMENT, TEACHERS AND PARENTS)

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Abstract: *Equitable education is very important in the delivery of education in this country. One of the government's efforts to accelerate the distribution of education is the establishment of the zoning system contained in Permendikbud No. 14 of 2018, namely the Acceptance of New Students (PPDB) which emphasizes the distance or radius between student homes and schools, so who is closer to the school he is more entitled to get educational services from the school. This research was conducted with the aim of describing and analyzing the implementation of zoning policies in the distribution of education. This research uses a qualitative research method with descriptive research type. The results showed that the implementation of the school zoning system was not yet fully implemented. It is seen that more negative impacts are felt by those involved in implementing this policy than positive impacts.*

Keywords: *Policy Implementation, Zoning, Equitable Education.*

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A. Introduction

Education is an integral part of development. The education process cannot be separated from the development process itself. The survival and progress of the nation, especially for developing countries, is determined by the progress or failure of education. This makes the role of education very important for every nation. As Indonesian citizens, education is the right of all nations in accordance with the 1945 Constitution, namely the government is obliged to fulfill the rights of its citizens in obtaining education to determine the future quality of life of a nation. Education is a strong foundation needed to achieve national progress and as a provision in facing the times in every process.¹ Education in the country has actually become one of the special concerns to see how equal access can be enjoyed by all citizens throughout Indonesia.

In access to education equality, there are two aspects that need to be considered, namely equality of opportunity to obtain education, namely access to education can be enjoyed by all residents of school age. Secondly, justice in obtaining the same education in society, namely education can be accessed by all ethnic groups, religions and groups equally.

In the implementation of education equality, we can see that schools in big cities have very advanced educational facilities and infrastructures, while those in villages or remote places are still

found facilities using makeshift facilities and infrastructure or even a lack of teaching staff. Whereas facilities and infrastructure are one of the most important resources in supporting the learning process at school, with good management of school facilities and infrastructure can improve the quality of education. Actually, this problem does not only occur in villages, even in urban areas we still find uneven education systems.

Based on this problem, there is a need to increase education equity, especially targeted at underprivileged and remote communities. Despite the fact that government programs continue to roll out from programs that began in 1884 regarding the equalization of elementary school education, then in 1994 compulsory nine-year education which is a continuation of the 6-year compulsory education program, then continued with the provision of scholarship programs, one of which encourages community involvement through the National Foster Parents movement, after that it continues to the School Operational Assistance Fund (BOS) and so on. This was followed by the provision of scholarship programs, one of which encouraged community involvement through the National Foster Parents Movement, and then on to the School Operational Assistance Fund (BOS) and so forth.

The government's effort to accelerate education equality is the establishment of a zoning system stated in Permendikbud Number 14 of 2018, namely the Acceptance of New Learners (PPDB) which emphasizes the distance or radius between the student's home and the school, thus whoever is closer to the school is more entitled to get education services from the school. This policy aims to accelerate equitable distribution of quality education

¹ H.A.R Tilaar, *Power and Education, National Education Management in the Vortex of Power*, Jakarta: Rineka Cipta Publisher, 2003, p.3.

and is expected to synergize the three centers of education, namely schools, communities and families to provide awareness to the general public that the responsibility for education is not only in one party, but a shared responsibility. The most important thing about zoning PPDB is that children can get education services closest to their homes or places of residence, if in one zone the quota is excess, the education office is obliged to find schools or open additional rombel, so that no child is left without a school.

The Ministry of Education and Culture says zoning is the main criterion in the New Student Admission (PPDB) for senior high schools. Zoning or school distance is a consideration for prospective students to be accepted. New Student Admission (PPDB) is currently based on a zoning system, in an effort to improve the education system so that the learning process takes place as effectively and efficiently as possible. For this reason, the criteria for passing new student candidates are based on zoning, not the results of the national exam.²

The implementation of the zoning-based PPDB policy is one of the right policies for equalizing access and quality of education because the principle is to bring education services closer to the community and equalize the quality of education. However, in reality, the implementation of this zoning system results in equalization of education only looking from one point of view, namely making it easier to guide and teach students, but racing in the field of diversity is very minimal. Where only the neighborhood around the school has the opportunity to graduate at the intended school. Then this zoning system raises cons such as smart and qualified children whose residences are close to non-favorite schools, of course they reluctantly accept to pursue education there. Many students also do not want to go to a school that is close to their home so they prefer private schools. In its implementation, the PPDB zoning system is still characterized by a number of problems.

B. Methods

The method used in this research is a qualitative method, this method was chosen because its elaborative nature can easily help researchers to dig deeper information related to a research topic. This research uses a descriptive type of research that seeks to describe and interpret what it is about the implementation of zoning policies in equalizing education. In this study, researchers aim to know and understand how the implementation of zoning policies in education equity efforts. The data taken in this research comes from various sources and research results related to the case under investigation.

C. Research Results and Discussion

The implementation of education in an area either in a macro scope such as a country or in a micro scope such as a region will certainly not be separated from the system that regulates the implementation of education to take place evenly throughout the scope of the area. The Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia is a very large unitary state that covers 1,922,570 km² (land only)

from 34 provinces.³ Meanwhile, the population in Indonesia according to data on the Official Website of the Republic of Indonesia in 2022 amounted to 275.77 million people.⁴ With a very large population within a very wide geographical coverage, it is certainly not easy for the Indonesian government to organize education evenly and thoroughly. The following are the results of research on education zoning from the perspectives of the government, teachers (schools) and parents presented descriptively.

Education zoning from the government's perspective

Indonesia's education system is clearly regulated in Law No. 20/2003 on the "National Education System". According to Law No. 20 of 2003, the national education system must be able to ensure equitable distribution of educational opportunities, improve the quality of education provision as well as relevance and efficiency in facing challenges in accordance with the demands of local, national, regional and global changes. Article 20 of Law No 11 of 2003 also requires the State Council and local governments to provide services and facilities and ensure the implementation of quality education for every citizen without discrimination.⁵ To answer these demands and challenges, the Indonesian government has launched an education zoning system so that education is comprehensive and equitable.

The zoning policy referred to in this case is the zoning system that applies to the implementation of PPDB (New Student Admission). The zoning system is an education policy that aims to ensure equal access to education services and equal quality of national education.⁶ New Learner Admission (PPDB) is one of the mechanisms for organizing the education system which is carried out when approaching the new school year, where there is a selection of prospective students carried out by the education unit based on the terms and conditions that apply to be accepted as students in the education unit.⁷ The Education zoning system in the implementation of PPDB has been regulated in Permendikbud Number 14 of 2018 which was revised in Permendikbud Number 51 of 2018. In the new Permendikbud, PPDB is implemented through three channels, namely zoning (minimum quota of 90 percent), achievement (maximum quota of 5 percent), and the transfer of parents of students (maximum quota of 5 percent). However, this article will discuss how the implementation of the PPDB zoning system is from the perspectives of the government,

³ "Central Statistics," accessed June 23, 2023, <https://www.bps.go.id/statictable/2014/09/05/1366/luas-daerah-dan-jumlah-pulau-menurut-provinsi-2002-2016.html>.

⁴ "Official Website of the Republic of Indonesia - Indonesia Information Portal," accessed June 23, 2023, <https://indonesia.go.id/mediapublik/detail/1953>.

⁵ Karmila, Mila, Niswatu Syakira, and Mahir Mahir. "Analysis of zoning system education policy in new student admissions." *Journal of mappesona* 3.1 (2020). Pp. 2.

⁶ "Zoning System," *BBPPMPV BMTI - Ministry of Education, Culture, Research and Technology* (blog), accessed June 23, 2023, <https://bbppmpvbmti.kemdikbud.go.id/main/sistem-zonasi/>.

⁷ Karmila, Mila, Niswatu Syakira, and Mahir Mahir. "Analysis of zoning system education policy in new student admissions." *Journal of mappesona* 3.1 (2020). Pp. 3.

² Jejen, Muslah., *Education Policy Analysis to Reduce the Crisis of National Character*. Jakarta: Kencana.2018. page 10.

teachers (schools) and parents based on the results of analysis in various research reports and articles that discuss it.

The implementation of the Education zoning system in PPDB from the government's perspective has been outlined in Permendikbud Number 14 of 2018 which has been revised with Permendikbud Number 51 of 2018. In general, there is no difference between Permendikbud No. 14/2018 and Permendikbud No. 51/2018, PPDB is still implemented through three channels, namely zoning (minimum quota of 90 percent), achievement (maximum quota of 5 percent), and transfer of parents of students (maximum quota of 5 percent). One of the differences in the new Permendikbud is the implementation of SKTM (Surat Keterangan Tidak Mampu) for students who come from poor families. SKTM serves to report the condition of the economic ability of the learner's family as evidenced by participation in the poor family handling program from the Government / Regional Government. This is because the zoning quota of at least 90% is also intended for students who are unable and have disabilities.⁸

The Minister of Education and Culture hopes that there will be a change in the pattern of PPDB in the following years. Schools and educational institutions are encouraged to be more active in registering school-age children in their respective zones. "We hope that there will be a change in the pattern of new student admissions from students registering with schools, to schools pro-actively registering or registering students, or prospective students. Therefore, Kemendikbud is trying to improve cooperation with the Ministry of Home Affairs, especially the Directorate General of Population and Civil Registry. Because the student base is actually from population data," he said.⁹ Furthermore, changes in population data will always be updated by Dukcapil online so that the zoning system data collection becomes easier.

In 2019 and 2020, the composition of the PPDB quota changed again. In the Regulation of the Ministry of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia Number 51 of 2018 and Regulation of the Ministry of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia Number 20 of 2019, the zoning pathway is reduced to 80%. Furthermore, the achievement pathway is given an additional 15% quota, and the pathway for the transfer of duties of parents or guardians receives 5%. The latest Permendikbud PPDB, Regulation of the Ministry of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia Number 44 of 2019, stipulates that the zoning pathway must reduce the quota to at least 50% of accepted students. In contrast, the achievement pathway is given an additional quota to a maximum of 30% based on UN scores or academic and non-academic achievements. The remaining 20% is divided into two pathways: an affirmation pathway of at least 15% and a transfer pathway for parents or guardians of a maximum of

5%.¹⁰

The Central Government of the Republic of Indonesia considered several things when making changes to the composition of the PPDB because local governments still face difficulties in achieving the minimum zoning pathway of 80%. To avoid schools lacking students, the zone unit was enlarged from one city to one zone. In addition, the government made various changes to education policies as a result of the low quality of education in Indonesia, such as the availability of teachers and school facilities.

Table 1. Zoning System Policy Changes

No	Year	Path	Quota
1	2017	Zoning	90 %
		Achievement	5 %
		Others	5 %
2	2018	Zoning	90 %
		Achievement	5 %
		Others	5 %
3	2019	Zoning	80 %
		Achievement	15 %
		Others	5 %
4	2020	Zoning	50 %
		Achievement	30 %
		Others	20 %

Source: Indonesian Ministry of Education and Culture (2020)

Education Zoning from the Teacher (school) perspective

While the implementation of the Education zoning system from the perspective of teachers (schools), this article presents the results of research by Pradewi and Rukiyati (2019) who conducted research on one of the favorite schools represented by SMA Cerdas and non-favorite represented by SMA Berbakat. The results of this research on education zoning include: (1) zoning facilitates access to education services, (2) zoning equalizes school quality, (3) zoning reduces school quality, (4) zoning is not suitable at the high school level, (5) the zoning system limits students choosing schools, (6) zoning policies must be accompanied by equitable distribution of educational facilities and infrastructure, and (7) zoning damages diversity.¹¹ From the results of this research, there are pros and cons of educators in the implementation of the zoning system. The results that support the zoning system are that zoning

⁸ "Permendikbud No. 51/2018 on New Student Admission at Kindergartens, Elementary Schools, Junior High Schools, Senior High Schools, and Vocational High Schools [JDIH BPK RI]," accessed June 23, 2023, <https://peraturan.bpk.go.id/Home/Details/138226/permendikbud-no-51-tahun-2018>.

⁹ "Zoning System."

¹⁰ "Permendikbud No. 44/2019 on New Student Admission at Kindergartens, Elementary Schools, Junior High Schools, Senior High Schools, and Vocational High Schools [JDIH BPK RI]," accessed June 23, 2023, <https://peraturan.go.id/id/permendikbud-no-44-tahun-2019>.

¹¹ Pradewi and Rukiyati, "The zoning system policy in an educational perspective", *JMSP (Journal of Education Management and Supervision)*, Vol. 4 No. 1 November 2019. Page. 31.

facilitates access to education services and zoning equalizes school quality. While the rest of the results of this study concluded that there were cons from educators against the implementation of the Education zoning system.

According to another study conducted by Risna et al (2020), there are benefits and disadvantages for schools that implement the Education zoning system in schools.

One of the benefits of the zoning policy is: (1) more students are active in practice rather than theory (according to some teachers); and (2) according to some teachers who benefit from the policy, more students find it difficult to understand and absorb material, so teachers have to create new learning methods to improve student scores below KKM. (3) more students are interested and motivated to participate in outdoor activities (according to some teachers).¹² And among the disadvantages are: (1) some teachers complain that many students score below the KKM (especially in subjects with a lot of theory); (2) more violations of discipline, such as skipping class, being late, fighting, and not wearing complete attributes, etc.; (3) it is considered more difficult to lead; (4) the emergence of new violations that have never happened before; and (5) low student fighting power, so that many zoning students, underestimate teachers, such as procrastinating on assignments; (6) lack of manners towards teachers; (7) teachers have difficulty conditioning the class, especially older teachers. (8) the formation of gangs from previous schools; (9) many fights outside school because students are familiar with environmental problems; (10) bad habits at home are brought to school; (11) almost every day the school gets reports on student offenses; (12) parental supervision has not been successful despite the close proximity of schools; and (13) school achievement has declined.¹³

The conclusion that can be drawn from the two studies above on how the Education zoning system from the teacher's perspective is that the application of the Education zoning system in schools still has minimal benefits and more losses caused to teachers (schools) that implement the zoning system. This can be seen from the comparison between the positive and negative impacts of the Education zoning system more negative impacts than positive impacts with a significant difference. Therefore, it is necessary to make many corrections and improvements in the application of the Education zoning system in the scope of teachers (schools).

Education zoning from the parents' perspective

Meanwhile, the implementation of the Education zoning system from the perspective of parents or in the broader scope of the community has generated more contra responses than pros. According to research conducted by Wahyuni (2018), the fierce debate that occurred in the community regarding the zoning system was divided into three major themes. First, the main objective is the distance between the home and school of prospective students as the main factor of PPDB is considered inadequate because the supply of schools in the area is not balanced, causing some schools to lack students. Second, there are differences in interpretation in

the application of zoning regulations, so the implementation varies in each school and region. Thirdly, the use of SKTM (Surat Keterangan Tidak Mampu), which in its application has many opportunities for fraud and cheating. There was also an incident in Yogyakarta where Yogyakarta parents made complaints to members of the DIY DPRD, to the Indonesian Ombudsman, and the Regional Ombudsman Institute (LOD) regarding the zoning system which was seen as discriminating against students' rights to school (Kusuma, 2019). A similar incident occurred in Malang city. The city's DPRD sent a protest to the Ministry of Education and Culture over complaints from the community who felt aggrieved because many students failed to enter the nearest school even though they were in the zoning system (Aminudin, 2019).¹⁴

The number of counter responses from the public did not discourage the government from continuing to implement the zoning system. Even when there was a change of Minister of Education and Culture Muhadjir Efendi to Nadiem Makarim, it did not dampen the government's intention to continue implementing the zoning system. According to some people who are also components of the zoning system, the long-term benefits that can be achieved from the implementation of this zoning system will far exceed the weaknesses that are currently felt (Safarah and Wibowo, 2018).¹⁵ This shows that the government's view of the implementation of the Education zoning system is too far to be reached by the community, so there needs to be a strong synergy between the government and the community in implementing this Education zoning system.

D. Conclusions and Suggestions

a. Summary

Reviewing the perspectives on the zoning system from the government, teachers (schools) and parents (communities), it was found that there were more cons from teachers (schools) as educators and from parents (communities) as supporters of education than pro responses to this policy. This shows that the government's good intentions and vision to equalize education provision are not maximized in its implementation. The lack of synergy between the government and teachers (schools) as educators and parents (communities) as supporters of education is lacking. This is because the government, teachers and parents are important frameworks that are inseparable in the conceptualization of education. A good synergy between these three elements is very important if you want to advance and equalize an education system. Moreover, Indonesia is a vast country with a very large population. So if you want this zoning system to work well, the government must be painstaking and patient in implementing it. In addition, teachers (schools) and parents (communities) must be patient and understand the government's efforts and efforts to advance and equalize education for all Indonesians without the term *stepchild*.

¹² Risna, Lisdahlia, and Syamsul Edi. "Analysis of zoning policy implementation in education equity." *Mappesona Journal* 3.1 (2020). Pp. 9.

¹³ *Ibid.* p. 10.

¹⁴ Syakarofath, Nandy Agustin, Ahmad Sulaiman, and Muhamad Faqih Irsyad. "A study of the pros and cons of implementing the education zoning system in Indonesia." *Journal of Education and Culture* 5.2 (2020) Page 117.

¹⁵ *Ibid.* p. 117.

Conceptual Framework of Education by (Pöder, et al., 2016)

b. Advice

There are suggestions for all parties involved in the implementation of this zoning policy so that later it can run optimally and really be able to realize the government's goal of equalizing education in Indonesia, namely:

- i. It is recommended that before issuing the policy, the government needs to prepare carefully, meaning that it needs to conduct socialization first. Then the percentage of quality in PPDB should be added so that the quota for outstanding students increases (achievement of UN results, academic, and non-academic), so that it can motivate student learning.
- ii. For the school, students with low input quality should be given special additional hours.
- iii. For the community, they should not do the existing studies to commit any fraud. From the many problems that have occurred, namely the many proven cases of KK changes and manipulations, this should be a warning so that they no longer commit fraud.

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